

The interplay of innovative leadership, innovative Work environment and organizational citizenship behavior

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the influence of innovative leadership and innovative work environments on the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees. To deepen the concept of the study, literature was reviewed. The study used assessment and correlational research design and thus weighted mean, Pearson r and ANOVA were used to analyze the data. The population of the study were the employees of the institution (DWCL). To gather the data, validated questionnaires were used. The study found that innovative leadership, innovative work environment and organizational citizenship behavior were high, however, there was no correlation between innovative leadership, innovative environment and organizational citizenship behavior. The study recognizes its limitation because of the limited variables investigated. Thus. the study recommends further study to identify other organizational factors and leadership that affect organizational citizenship behavior.

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Introduction

Enhancing employee loyalty and commitment is vital for organizational success, requiring attention to various factors like treatment, compensation, and working conditions. Loyalty and commitment are influenced by multiple organizational aspects, not solely by salary. Additionally, fostering organizational citizenship behavior

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(Aloustani, et al., 2020), where employees exceed job requirements, is crucial. This behavior, linked to leadership, ethical climate (Huang, et al., 2021, Nemr, et al., 2021, Fatima & Siddiqui, 2019, Ali, et al., 2018) on organizational citizenship behavior and work environment, remains underexplored concerning its relation to innovative leadership and work environments. Hence, this study investigates how innovative leadership and environments affect organizational citizenship behavior, with implications for training and development. (Hasani, et al., 2013; Nguyen, et al., 2022; Grego-Planer, 2019). The study comprises an introduction, literature review, research methodology, data analysis, and discussion

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to expand and deepen the understanding of the concept and theories of the current study which will help establish the theories of the study to be investigated. The result of the review is presented thematically according to the theme of the current study.

The Concept of Leadership

When failure occurs, the organization's leader bears the blame, as noted by Peter Drucker, cited by Hesselbein (2010). This assertion is supported by studies showing leadership's impact on organizational performance (Liebersson & O'Connor, 1972; Jing & Avery, 2008; Hurduzeu, 2015; Karamat, 2013). Leadership responsibility extends to navigating challenges posed by the external environment, requiring adaptability and innovation. Traditional trait theories suggest leadership is innate, emphasizing traits like self-confidence and intelligence (Stodgill, 1948; Tannenbaum and Schmidt, 1973; Harter, 2008). However, behavioral theories argue leaders can be developed through training and experience (Ruvolo et al., 2004), fostering people- and task-oriented approaches (Lewin et al., 1939; Blake and Mouton, 1964, 1985; Kouzes and Posner, 1995). Situational and contingency theories underscore the importance of adapting leadership style to the situation (Khan et al., 2016). Definitions of leadership highlight its role in influencing others towards common goals (Rost, 1991; Kouzes and Posner, 1995). In the 21st century, leadership demands adaptability to rapid environmental changes, necessitating innovative traits like creativity and flexibility (Stodgill, 1948; Tannenbaum and Schmidt, 1973; Harter, 2008; Gardner, 1989; Toegel and Barsoux, 2013). This blend of traits, behaviors, and situational judgment characterizes innovative leadership.

Innovation and Innovative Leadership

To grasp the essence of innovative leadership, one must understand the concept of innovation, intricately linked to rapid environmental changes like market and technological evolution (Suarez & Lanzolla, 2007). Innovation, as defined by Merriam-Webster and The New Oxford Dictionary of English, involves introducing something new or making changes to existing products or services (Gorbo, 2022; O'Sullivan & Dooley, 2008). With market and technology changes occurring swiftly, innovative organizational leadership becomes imperative, characterized by responsiveness to new trends and the application of creative thinking to generate new ideas (Baumgartner, 2011). An innovative leader fosters a culture of creativity and innovation among employees, recognizing that employee creativity is crucial for organizational success and competitiveness (Gliddon, 2006; Lv, et al., 2021). By prioritizing an environment conducive to creative efforts over rigid structures, innovative leaders stimulate imagination, encourage collaboration, and drive growth through innovation (Amabile & Khair, 2008; Barsh, et al., 2008; Mumford & Licuanan, 2004). In today's dynamic landscape, organizations require leaders who are attuned to external and internal trends and who prioritize innovation over bureaucracy to ensure competitiveness and survival (Barsh, et al., 2008). Thus, an innovative leader serves as both an idea generator and an influencer, essential for fostering innovation within the organization.

The Concept of Work Environment

Since the 1900s, the relationship between work environment and productivity has been a focal point for management and researchers. Initially, the focus was on the physical work environment, leading to improvements in office setups such as lighting. However, attention shifted towards task performance and human relations after realizing that physical improvements alone didn't significantly impact productivity. Elton Mayo's study at the Hawthorne plant marked a shift towards considering human psychological needs in the work environment, emphasizing the importance of employee satisfaction and attention from employers (Mayo, 1930, cited by Smith, 1987). Over time, the concept of work environment expanded to include communications, conflict resolution, and cooperation among organizational members (Walden, 2004). Definitions vary, with some focusing on human relations (Raziq and Maulabakhsh, 2015), others on physical aspects (Salunke, 2015), and some emphasizing the setting where employees perform their tasks (Kohun, 1992).

Recent studies have consistently shown a positive correlation between the work environment and job performance, satisfaction, and productivity (Demus et al., 2015; Jayaweera, 2015; Al-Omari and Okasheh, 2017; Rachman, 2021). Further research by Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015), Agbozo et al. (2015), Taheri et al. (2020), Pandey (2017), and Kamanja et al. (2019) reinforces these findings, highlighting the significant impact of a positive work environment on various aspects of employee behavior. Neglecting the work environment may hinder job performance and impede organizational success. Hence, management must prioritize improving the work environment to foster positive outcomes.

The Innovative Work Environment

The concept of an innovative work environment differs from the general work environment. While the latter encompasses both physical and psychological aspects, the former specifically fosters innovative ideas and behaviors. Several studies have explored the impact of an innovative work environment on job satisfaction, yet a clear definition of this concept is often lacking (Mckinnon et al., 2003; Zhou et al., 2005; Berson, Oreg, & Dvir, 2008). Rogovski (2021) defines it as an environment that encourages unorthodox thinking, fostering a culture where challenging norms is valued. This perspective emphasizes an organizational climate oriented towards innovation (Litwin, 1968; Xu et al., 2022). Within such climates, trust among members facilitates cooperation and knowledge sharing, crucial for generating new ideas (Johannessen & Olsen, 2011; Khan, 1990). Studies suggest that a friendly organizational climate reduces stress and enhances job satisfaction and commitment (Farr & West, 1991). Additionally, intrinsic motivation is vital for fostering creativity and innovation (Hennessey & Amabile, 1998). Research also indicates a positive correlation between an innovative organizational culture and performance (Ur Rehman et al., 2019; Aboramadan et al., 2020; Naranjo-Valencia et al., 2016). Therefore, fostering an innovative work environment is essential for organizational success.

Overview of Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The concept of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) originates from political philosophy, where citizenship entails obedience, loyalty, and participation (Graham, 1991). In an organizational context, this translates to organizational obedience, loyalty, and participation (Inkeles, 1969). Early research by Bateman & Organ (1983) and Smith, Organ, & Near (1983); Abun (2021) defined OCB as behaviors beyond role requirements for the organization's benefit, aligning with citizenship ideals. Katz (1964) emphasized cooperative and spontaneous actions beyond prescribed roles, crucial for organizational functioning. Subsequent efforts identified dimensions of OCB, focusing on loyalty and participation (Organ & Ryan, 1995). Organ (1988) and Abun (2021) identified conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy, and altruism as dimensions, later expanded by Podsakoff et al. (2000). Fox and Specter (2002) consolidated these dimensions into altruistic behavior, encompassing both

helping others and the organization. Thus, OCB encompasses behaviors beneficial to both individuals and the organization.

Conceptual Framework

Statement of the Problems

The study determined the effect of innovative leadership and innovative work environments on the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the innovative leadership of the administrators?
2. What is the innovative work environment of the institution in terms of:
 - a. work practices
 - b. promoting innovation
 - c. Physical environment
 - d. Providing learning opportunities
3. What is the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of:
 - a. OCBP
 - b. OCBO
4. Is there a relationship between innovative leadership and organizational citizenship behavior?
5. Is there a relationship between an innovative work environment and organizational citizenship behavior?

Assumptions

The study assumes that innovative leadership and an innovative work environment motivate employees to develop a behavior that benefits the organization and other employees

Hypothesis

Leadership and the work environment have a significant impact on employee behavior. Positive leadership and a supportive environment can encourage employees to remain committed to the organization. Conversely, negative leadership and a toxic environment can deter employees from exerting their full effort for the organization's

success. Therefore, the present study hypothesizes that innovative leadership and an innovative work environment influence employees' organizational citizenship behavior.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limits its investigation only to the effect of innovative leadership and innovative environment on the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag.

Research Methodology

In adherence to established research standards, this study employs a structured research methodology, as advocated by Wilkinson (2000) and Leedy (1974). Research methodology entails employing specific methods to identify, select, and analyze data pertinent to the study's focus. Accordingly, this research adopts various investigative methods, including research design, data collection instruments, target population, study location, data collection procedures, and statistical data analysis techniques.

Research Design of the Study

The research design employed in this study is a descriptive correlational research design, as outlined by Ariola (2006). Descriptive correlational research aims to elucidate relationships among variables without establishing causal connections. In essence, descriptive research endeavors to portray a population, situation, or phenomenon, often answering questions pertaining to what, when, how, and where, rather than why (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. This college is located in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The study's participants consist of the college's employees. Due to the manageable number of employees, the study utilized total enumeration sampling, encompassing all faculty and staff from the college as respondents.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires by the Australian Government (2022) on the innovative environment, and Spector and Fox (2002) on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Data Gathering Procedures

In adherence to scientific standards, data collection commenced after obtaining approval from the college Presidents. The researcher formally requested permission via letter, which was subsequently granted. Following approval, questionnaires were distributed by a designated representative. Upon completion, data was collected by the college representative and forwarded to the researcher for analysis and tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study proceeded following approval from the research ethics committee, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and the prevention of harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. The weighted mean served to assess the levels of innovative leadership style, innovative work environment, and organizational citizenship behavior among employees. Additionally, Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were utilized to examine the relationships between innovative leadership, innovative work environment, and organizational citizenship behavior. The resulting values will be interpreted descriptively according to the following ranges:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	strongly agree/ Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree / High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/ Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

The following are the data gathered through questionnaires. The presentation follows the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: 1. What is the innovative leadership of the administrators?

Table 1. Innovative leadership of the administration of Divine Word College of Laoag (n= 152)

Indicators	Weighted mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Make innovation an integral part of leadership and management activities	4.12	A/H
Demonstrate positive reception of ideas from others and provide constructive advice	4.12	A/H
Establish and maintain a relationship based on mutual respect and trust	4.14	A/H
Takes considered risks to open up opportunities for innovation	4.14	A/H
Consult on and establish working conditions that reflect and encourage innovative practice	4.13	A/H
Introduce and maintain workplace procedures that foster innovation and allow for rigorous evaluation of innovative ideas	4.08	A/H
Build and lead teams to work in ways that maximize opportunities for innovation	4.08	A/H
Acknowledge suggestions, improvements and innovations from subordinates	4.09	A/H
Find appropriate ways of celebrating and promoting innovations/changes	4.13	A/H
Pro-actively share relevant information, knowledge and skills with the subordinates	4.00	A/H
Composite Mean	4.10	A/H

Source: Australian Government (2022).

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	strongly agree/ Very High

3.41-4.20	Agree / High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/ Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Based on the data, administrators' innovative leadership received an overall composite mean rating of 4.10, indicating a high level of agreement among employees. This suggests that administrators have effectively integrated innovation into their leadership approach, as evidenced by their positive reception of new ideas, willingness to take risks, and efforts to foster a culture of innovation. Research has consistently shown that innovative leadership contributes to organizational change, improved employee performance, and enhanced innovative behavior among employees.

Problem 2: What is the innovative work environment of the Divine Word College of Laoag?

Table 2. The innovative work environment of the Divine Word College of Laoag (n=152)

INNOVATIVE WORK ENVIRONMENT		WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A	Work Practices		
1.	Consult and establish working conditions that reflect and encourage innovative practice.	3.98	A/H
2.	Introduce and maintain workplace procedures that foster innovation and allow for rigorous evaluation of innovative ideas	4.00	A/H
3.	Facilitate and participate in collaborative work arrangements to foster innovation	4.00	A/H
4.	Build and lead teams to work in ways that maximize opportunities for innovation	4.02	A/H
Composite Mean		4.00	A/H
B.	Promoting Innovation		
1.	Acknowledge suggestions, improvements and innovations from all colleagues	4.08	A/H
2.	Find appropriate ways of celebrating and promoting innovation	4.05	A/H
3.	Promote and reinforce the value of innovation according to the vision and objectives of the organization	4.07	A/H
4.	Promote and support the evaluation of innovative ideas within the wider organizational context	4.09	A/H
Composite Mean		4.07	A/H
C.	Physical Environment		
1.	Evaluate the impact of the physical environment on innovation	3.97	A/H
2.	Collaborate with colleagues about ideas for enhancing the physical work environment before taking actions	4.02	A/H
3.	Consider the potential for supporting innovation when selecting physical resources and equipment	3.99	A/H
4.	Design, fit out and decorate workspaces to encourage creative mindsets, collaborative	4.00	A/H

	working and the development of positive workplace relationships		
	Composite Mean	4.00	A/H
D.	Providing Learning Opportunities		
1.	Pro-actively share relevant information, knowledge and skills with colleagues	3.96	A/H
2.	Provide or encourage formal and informal learning opportunities to help develop the skills needed for innovation environment before taking actions	4.00	A/H
3.	Create opportunities in which individuals can learn from the experience of others.	3.96	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.97	A/H
	OVERALL MEAN	4.01	

Source: Australian Government (2022).

The data in the table indicates that the Divine Word College of Laoag's innovative work environment has a composite mean rating of 4.01, signifying a high level of agreement among employees. This rating suggests that while the institution's innovative work environment is not exceptionally high, it is still considered high overall. Employees perceive that administrators encourage innovative practices through workplace procedures, collaborative arrangements, and learning opportunities. Additionally, administrators are seen as receptive to suggestions for improvement and actively promote innovation. Research supports the notion that an innovative work environment contributes to improved employee innovative behavior and organizational performance (Abun et al., 2023; Shanker et al., 2017).

Table 3: Organizational Citizenship Behavior that directs toward a person (OCBP)

Indicators	Weighted mean	Descriptive interpretations
Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a work problem	3.67	A/H
Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a personal problem	3.66	A/H
Change vacation schedules, workdays, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs	3.66	A/H
Help a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects	3.70	A/H
Went out of the way to encourage co-workers or express appreciation	3.64	A/H
Defended co-worker who was being 'put down' or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors	3.70	A/H
Help co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks	3.68	A/H
Lent money or personal property to a co-worker	3.64	A/H
Composite mean	3.66	A/H

Source: Spector and Fox (2002).

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree/very high
3.41 - 4.20	Agree
2.61 - 3.40	somewhat agree
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree

According to the data in the table, the employees' organizational citizenship behavior related to OCBP (concern for others) has a composite mean rating of 3.66, indicating an "agree/high" level. This rating suggests that while the employees' behavior in this regard is not exceptionally high, it is still considered high overall. Employees demonstrate compassion by offering support to colleagues facing personal or work-related challenges, sacrificing

their time to assist others, and defending coworkers when needed. Research by Ashforth et al. (2000) and Simpson et al. (2013) highlights the importance of shared values that prioritize care, fostering a culture where individuals are more inclined to alleviate suffering. Dutton et al. (2014) further emphasize the need for organizations and individuals to minimize barriers and increase awareness of colleagues' challenges, fostering a culture of compassion.

Table 4: Organizational citizenship behavior that directs toward the organization (OCBO).

Indicators	Weighted mean	Descriptive interpretation
Help new employees get oriented to the job	3.76	A/H
Offered suggestions to improve how work is done	3.67	A/H
Volunteered for extra work assignments	3.60	A/H
Said good things about your employer in front of others	3.69	A/H
Said good things about your school in the community outside the school	3.70	A/H
Give up meals and other breaks to complete the work	3.64	A/H
Offered suggestions for improving the work environment	3.72	A/H
came in early or stayed late without pay to complete a project or task	3.64	A/H
Volunteer to share new job knowledge or skills with other employees	3.64	A/H
Composite mean	3.67	A/H
Overall Mean Rating (OCBP & OCBO).	3.67	A/H

Source: Spector and Fox (2002)

Problem 4. Is there a relationship between innovative leadership and organizational citizenship behavior?

Table 5: Relationship Between Innovative Leadership of Administration and Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Employees

A. Innovative Leadership of Administration and Acts that are directed toward the Person

(OCBP)

The obtained correlation coefficient of .065 which is lower than the tabular value of r at .05 level of significance on the test or relationship between innovative leadership of the administration and employees' organizational citizenship behavior in terms of acts that direct toward the person (OCBP) indicates that they are not significantly related. Therefore, regardless of the degree of innovative leadership of the administration, the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of OCBP will be the same.

B. Innovative Leadership of administration and Acts that Direct Toward the Organization

(OCBO)

The results of the correlation analysis between the innovative leadership of the administration and the employees' organizational citizenship behavior in terms of OCBO revealed that they are not significantly related (r=.039). This implies that regardless of the level of innovative leadership of the administration the employees' OCBO remains the same.

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES	INNOVATIVE LEADERSHIP OF ADMINISTRATION	
Acts that Direct Toward the Person (OCBP)	r	.065
	(Sig. 2 - tailed)	.428
Acts that Direct Toward the organization (OCBO)	r	.039

(Sig. 2-tailed) .634

* Significant at .05 level of significance (2-tailed)
 ** Significant at .01 level of significance (2-tailed)

Problem 5: Is there a relationship between an innovative work environment and organizational citizenship behavior?

Table 6: Relationships Between Innovative Work Environments and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Innovative Work Environments and OCBP

The multiple linear regression analysis between the four factors of innovative work environments in terms of work practices, promoting innovation, physical environment, and providing learning opportunities taken as a group indicates that these factors could not predict the employees' OCBP, $F(4,147) = 1.234, p > .05$, with 3.20 per cent overlap between the predictor variables and employees' OCBP.

This implies that the employees' OCBP remains the same regardless of the changes in the employees' innovative work environments along with work practices, promoting innovation, physical environment, and providing learning opportunities. Thus, the recorded variations in the employees' OCBP are not attributed to the differences in the work environments.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.180 ^a	.032	.006	.48836

a. Predictors: (Constant), Providing Learning Opportunities, Promoting Innovation, Physical Environment, Work Practices

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.177	4	.294	1.234	.299 ^b
	Residual	35.059	147	.238		
	Total	36.236	151			

a. Dependent Variable: OCBP

b. Predictors: (Constant), Providing Learning Opportunities, Promoting Innovation, Physical Environment, Work Practices

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.956	.267		14.801	.000
	Work Practices	-.101	.123	-.131	-.821	.413
	Promoting Innovation	.178	.107	.247	1.659	.099
	Physical Environment	-.055	.104	-.084	-.528	.599
	Providing Learning Opportunities	-.098	.113	-.132	-.867	.387

a. Dependent Variable: OCBP

Table 7: Innovative Work Environments and OCBO

The four elements of innovative work environments such as work practices, promoting innovation, physical environment, and providing learning opportunities taken as a group do not predict the employee's OCBO. This is reflected by the obtained $F(4, 147) = 0.917, p > .05$, with a 2.40 per cent overlap between the predictor variables and OCBO.

This signifies that the observed differences in the employees' OCBO are not due to the varying levels in their work environments in terms of work practices, promoting innovation, physical environment, and providing learning opportunities.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.156 ^a	.024	-.002	.49149

a. Predictors: (Constant), Providing Learning Opportunities, Promoting Innovation, Physical Environment, Work Practices

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.886	4	.221	.917	.456 ^b
	Residual	35.510	147	.242		
	Total	36.395	151			

a. Dependent Variable: OCBO

b. Predictors: (Constant), Providing Learning Opportunities, Promoting Innovation, Physical Environment, Work Practices

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.934	.269		14.625	.000
	Work Practices	-.023	.123	-.030	-.189	.851
	Promoting Innovation	.121	.108	.168	1.125	.262
	Physical Environment	-.009	.105	-.014	-.089	.929
	Providing Learning Opportunities	-.157	.113	-.211	-1.384	.169

a. Dependent Variable: OCBO

Results and Discussions

The results indicate that while innovative leadership, innovative work environment, and organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBP and OCBO) of the employees are rated high, they are not significantly correlated. This suggests that improvements in innovative leadership and work environment do not predict an increase in organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, enhancing OCB may require focusing on other organizational factors.

Organizational citizenship behavior is crucial for organizational performance (Sadeghi, 2016), prompting management to explore alternative strategies. For the Divine Word College of Laoag, priorities may include empowering leadership (Jiang et al., 2019), transformational leadership (Khaola & Sephelane, 2013), and job satisfaction (Fitrio et al., 2019) as avenues for enhancing OCB.

Conclusion

The study sought to investigate the impact of innovative leadership and work environments on employee organizational citizenship behavior. Findings revealed high ratings for innovative leadership, innovative work environments, and organizational citizenship behavior. However, the analysis showed that neither innovative leadership nor innovative work environments were significantly correlated with organizational citizenship behavior. The study acknowledges its limitation in solely assessing these dimensions and recommends further research into other leadership and work environment factors affecting organizational citizenship behavior.

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